

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

Fargana Aliyeva Aydın

Docent of the "Language Training" department of the Police Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Azerbaijan, doctor of philosophy in Philology

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WAYS TO DEVELOP PUBLIC SPEAKING SKILLS, THE IMPORTANCE OF COMMUNICATION TOOLS AND SPEECH TECHNIQUES

Summary:

The article discusses the ways, methods and tools for developing students' oral and written speech skills. It is emphasized that in order for every intellectual to master the skill of giving a speech, it is of great importance to know the language he speaks well, as well as how to use communication tools, body language, and speech techniques. The article emphasizes the importance of gestures and facial expressions, body language, diction, voice, timbre, intonation, expression and pause in mastering the art of oratory and giving a speech. Using these tools correctly serves to fully convey one's feelings and emotions, and purpose to the audience during a speech. When talking about the ways to develop oratory skills, it is discussed about eliminating subconscious fear during a speech and developing spontaneous speeches.

Key words: *Speaker, speech, intonation, means of communication, diction, speech, subconscious fear*

Discussion. The mother tongue is not only a means of communication, but also a means of expressing the worldview, way of thinking, and spiritual existence of the people in general. Business communication in society, ethical rules of speech and the construction of speech in accordance with it, and the preparation of reports or presentations on the work done are the main requirements of the era.

Every intellectual must be able to express his thoughts accurately, concisely and beautifully. It is impossible to master oratory skills without studying the conformity of speech to the norms of literary language, the ability to use the means and possibilities of expression of the language in accordance with the purpose and content of speech; the problems of formation and improvement of the system of language levels and units included in them, the development line of language phenomena and processes, speech techniques, stylistics, paralinguistic means.

In general, a modern person should be deeply familiar with the language, skillfully using speech techniques and body language to convince the people in front of him. This is a person's high culture of thinking, a conscious love of language, the highest quality. A person's speech is the main tool that reveals his inner world and professionalism. In order to get to know people and get to know them well, you need to communicate and be in contact. The great philosopher of antiquity, Socrates, used to say: "O man, speak so that I may know you!"

Today, in the conditions of globalization, the biggest problem of the 21st century is that communication is carried out not verbally, but rather through written social platforms. The speech of a student who studies various foreign languages without developing his speech in his native language is not clear and fluent. Not only the speech of a student studying in a foreign language school, but also his perspective on the world is shaped by the customs, traditions, culture,

and values of that people. National thinking, national ideology are fragmented here. The death of a language is equal to the death of a people. The correct solution to this problem lies in the policy of using the language at the state level.

Development of the problem. If we look at the degree of development of the problem, we will see that in Greece, the cradle of oratory, outstanding orators were trained and the theory of oratory was created even before our era. In 335 BC, Aristotle wrote his work "Rhetoric" and gave the scientific foundations of the art of oratory, evaluated the art as a special type of human activity, and explained in detail the structure, style, orthoepy, expressive means, etc. of the orator's speech. [3]

In their scientific works on speech culture, Azerbaijani philologists Adil Babayev, Nadir Abdullayev, Fikrat Shiriyev, Nadir Mammadli, Buludkhan Khalilov and other scholars have provided theoretical information on the history of oratory, oratory skills, means of communication, expressiveness of speech, and various speech techniques.

Adil Babayev's book "Azerbaijani Language and Speech Culture" discusses the history of oratory, the stages of development of our language, and the state's care for the language, and justifies the fact that the foundation of science began in Greece, and the development of people's speech as a result of Solon's laws. This book also discusses practical language rules. [2]

In his book "Fundamentals of Speech Culture", Nadir Abdullayev explained the qualities of speech - expressiveness, clarity, fluency, conciseness, etc., and provided information about the types and forms of speech. The scope of activity of the oral language is of great importance for the observance of literary pronunciation norms. It is substantiated how writers and poets who share their desires and wishes, feelings

and excitement with their readers at literary and artistic evenings, prominent actors performing on the theater stage, announcers who constantly communicate with the public through radio and television programs, teachers who master the basics of knowledge and instill high moral qualities in students and pupils, orators who speak about issues of state importance from the lectern, diplomats and lawyers use the rich opportunities of the oral literary language. [1]

Fikrat Shiriyeu, in his book "Speech Culture and Rhetoric of the Azerbaijani Language," extensively researched the means of communication, composition of speech, and topics of public speaking. He noted the regulation of emotionality depending on the goals and objectives of oral reasoning. [6]

Purpose of the study: It consists of methods for developing public speaking skills, ways to use communication tools and speech techniques.

Research methods: Research methods such as theoretical analysis and generalization, and observation were used during the course of the work.

Main part: Ways to develop public speaking skills. After studying the opinions of various scholars about the important factors for becoming a speaker, it can be concluded that everything done, from the pre-speech stage, to the preparation for the speech, to the appearance on stage, and the proper management of speech skills, all serve to deliver a perfect speech.

When giving a speech, everyone should be able to express their thoughts correctly, accurately, and clearly, as well as convey them to the listener in an effective, emotional, and convincing way, and to use language tools that can penetrate the hearts and minds of the audience. A bright, original, and expressive speech affects the feelings of the listeners, attracts their attention, and helps them understand the content well. Students are satisfied with the lectures of a number of teachers and speakers because their speech is clear and meaningful. This speech consists of strong logic, coherent words and sentences, and is also convincing, effective, and emotional.

There are internal and external parameters of speech. The speaker must be able to use these parameters correctly. The energy parameter, that is, the parameters of emotional, passionate speech, tone of voice, pace, pause, enthusiasm, body language, used in a timely and skillful manner, attracts the attention of the listener.

Intonation is the most characteristic pronunciation phenomenon that is directly related to both the speech and reading process. In the process of communication, the speaker gives his speech a different sound arrangement in order to achieve his goal. In other words, in the process of speech, our speech has colorful intonation shades.

In the process of reading, the situation is somewhat different. In the written form of speech, only the results of the author's logical thinking are given. Here, the reader's goal is to reveal the author's idea given in writing, to voice it. Intonation creates such subtle emotional relationships in speech that no formal sign can create it. Intonation can not only increase the impact of a sentence, an expression, or a single word,

but also distort the meaning it actually expresses, or cause it to be understood in a completely opposite sense.

From what we have said, we come to the conclusion that, as the French phonetician Grammont said, "the words that form sentences are only their "skeleton", it is intonation that gives movement and life to this skeleton.

Sometimes during speech we encounter high-pitched or low-tempo speech, incorrect pauses, incorrect pace and breathing. Such defects in intonation and expressiveness of speech reduce the quality of the speaker's speech, lead to misunderstanding of the content of the speech and distraction.

Correct regulation of breathing and voice is one of the important conditions in the pronunciation process. In particular, improper breathing during speech leads to shortness of breath, shortness of breath, and impaired diction. To avoid this, first of all, normal pauses in speech should be observed.

Speech pauses are of great importance not only for the speaker, but also for the listener. The listener, in turn, understands what he hears during the pause made by the speaker. Therefore, in order to ensure the listener's understanding, it is necessary to use pauses, tone of voice, and intonation correctly.

In order to achieve success in the modern era, along with knowledge and skills, "soft skills" are skills that help solve life problems and work with other people. (understanding, communication, emotional intelligence, etc.) The term "soft skills" is used in contrast to the term "hard skills" (professional skills needed to solve specific problems in the work process). Having professional skills is a must, while soft skills make you different from everyone else. Soft skills include personal skills and communication skills, people management skills. These skills are also essential for a good specialist and a good speaker. It includes the ability to capture people with your speech, worldview, and effective communication, as well as the ability to listen, adjust body language, facial expressions, and tone of voice. IQ-intelligence, emotional intelligence are also of particular importance for high communication skills.

Overcoming the subconscious fear in people before a speech is the way to a great speech. The reason for this is that we think subconsciously and increase our excitement by asking ourselves questions like "Maybe I forgot everything? Am I not well prepared? Will they listen to me?". Talking to the subconscious is also an important tool that prepares a person for a speech. Our subconscious thoughts control us 99%. So how can we please the subconscious? By giving ourselves confidence, by beating off excitement with our thoughts, by shaking off the excitement with our hands, by thinking that the people in front of us – the listeners – are on the same level as us, or by thinking as if we are talking to friends, we overcome fear during our speech and speech. If we go over the fear before the speech, by doing breathing exercises and punching, we prepare ourselves for the speech. Napoleon said: "A person who cannot speak in front of a public cannot achieve success in his career."

The path to success also consists of appearance (body language, gesture, facial expressions, posture, clothing), words (meaning) and voice (expression style, speech events). During our speech, words constitute 10%, voice -35%, and body language -55%. When using body language skillfully, the correctness and appropriateness of gestures, facial expressions and posture are important factors for the perfection of our speeches.

When standing, one leg slightly forward and the other behind helps to maintain a straight posture. At this time, 60% of our weight should be on the front leg and 40% on the back leg. The shoulders should be straight, and it is necessary to use coordinating and regulating gestures and facial expressions appropriate to the topic.

It is important to note that the eyebrows and lips play a key role in understanding a person's true emotions. It has been scientifically proven that the left side of the face reflects human emotions more quickly; this is due to the fact that the right hemisphere of the brain, which controls a person's emotional life, controls the muscles on the left side of the face. Positive emotions are reflected on both sides of the face to one degree or another, while negative emotions are more pronounced on the left side of the face.

There are also micro-gestures: eye movement, reddening of the neck, increased number of blinks, lip twitching, etc. These micro-gestures occur when a

person is insecure or loses himself/herself during a speech.

It is important to maintain eye contact with the audience while giving a speech, to have them in the spotlight. This encourages you to communicate freely with the audience and attract their attention.

It is possible to overcome anxiety by speaking in front of a mirror, but it is not possible to develop much when you see your own flaws. D. Carnegie divides people into 3 groups in front of a mirror: shameful speakers, beautiful speakers, objective speakers.

The first group of people treat their speech very badly, see only the bad and fear increases. They cannot get rid of shameful thoughts. In the second group, people pay attention to their beauty, and the speech is forgotten. The third group of people approach everything objectively, see their mistakes and try to eliminate them.

Methods to improve our speech. Word association (daisy method) Using this method, we can improve our spontaneous speeches. For example; When talking about language, we write on the petals of a daisy what issues we will touch on: means of communication, history and formation, genealogical and typological features, vocabulary composition, speech culture, alphabet, etc. If we can build a 2-minute speech by talking about such issues, then we can gradually enrich our speeches and expand them to 10 minutes.

Result: In the conditions of independence, the state policy of the country was aimed at ensuring the conditions for the full functioning of the language as the most important means of communication. As a result of the care for the language of our national leader Heydar Aliyev, the Azerbaijani language has become widely used in all state structures, institutions and enterprises, and educational institutions, both written and oral:

1. At such a moment, every Azerbaijani intellectual and young person should be deeply familiar with their native language in order to speak skillfully in their native language and master the skills of giving speeches.

2. A person's speech culture plays an important role in the speech process. One of its tasks is to make a pleasant impression on the listener, and based on a person's speech, it is possible to say something about

his/her level of spiritual and intellectual development, his inner culture. Therefore, in order to have a beautiful speech, a person must know the vocabulary of the language he speaks, the norms of the literary language, and the stylistics, as well as be able to skillfully use paralinguistic means.

3. A modern Azerbaijani young person should have soft skills, use speech techniques - voice, breathing, expression, pauses correctly, and pay attention to his appearance and posture.

4. S/He should read and practice to develop his spontaneous speeches.

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